

Intimate Transactions in Care Work: Precarity, Purpose and Pleasure

Abstract

Accelerated ageing of the oldest old, longer lifespan, splintering of informal family network that acted as support planks and dearth of formal social care, route to seeking different pathways to tackle the ‘care crisis’. Preference for ‘ageing in place’ and a familiar environmental setting precipitates into affirming for ageing and dying within the precincts of home. In this context, ayah-centred carework is gaining momentum to manage urban ageing, an alternative response, often as a complement, supplement or substitution to the traditional, intergenerational family care. With private home, turning to a workplace for paid intimate carework, the entanglements, complexities and unsettling nature of the discourses of body, care, home and gendered labour interpenetrates each other. While care crisis of the older citizenry is a red alert, the working conditions of the ayahs reeks of precarity, as the latter confront and adapt to recalcitrant substances, and the threat to the violations of their integrity. While ayahs etch out strategies oriented towards intimate care, the paper, through ethnographic qualitative interviews, strives to position ayahs as rights-bearing citizens whose contribution, resilience and micro-resistances cast light on the contradictions of devaluation and indispensability of intimate carework for older people.

Keywords:

Ayahs, homecare in India, old-age care, repulsion, intimate labour

Background and Context: Ageing in India and the care conundrum

The resilience approach to old-age evinces that the oldest old or the super agers¹ show a higher a threshold for disease and stunted pace of disease progression (Ostwald and Dyer, 2011). Robust interventions in healthcare and control of higher incidence of infectious diseases resulted in an epidemiological transition defined by low mortality rate or compression of morbidity through delaying disease onset (Fries, 1983), ‘rectangularization of the survival curve’ (Hayflick, 1980)² and increase in life span. Technologization through installation of pacemakers and dialysis machines for kidneys has extended human survival and contributed to a new category known as cyborgs or bionic bodies (Helman, 2007). However, a longer lifespan can amount to living with morbidities, requiring assistance and a compatible support architecture, and therefore not an indicator of high quality of life (QoL). This necessitates a

¹ Super-agers refer to those in the category of 70 to 80 years.

² This refers to the increase in life expectancy that is same to the maximum lifespan.

deeper examination into the long-term care (LTC) of an ageing demography among policymakers, demographers, gerontologists and geriatricians.

In India, there are a number of unmet healthcare needs of older people as geriatric specialties and facilities are yet to fully develop. Low competence of the public health systems especially PHCs (primary healthcare sector) to address the health issues of a growing number of older people, high out-of-pocket expenditure (OOPE) with increased incidence of geriatric disease burden and severity of sickness (Sadanandan, 2022) and burgeoning of the ‘for-profit’ private healthcare sector through commercialisation, corporatisation and marketisation (Baru, 2003) lever towards alternative, extra-ageing relatively low-cost home-based services. Taking stock of the preparedness in preventive, curative and rehabilitative healthcare services is exigent to respond and address to issues affecting older people across the spectrum of gender, region, caste, ethnicity, economic resources, social capital and health condition.

Despite the structural changes within family, the streams of global demographic transition, population maturation and families ‘living apart’ have re-emphasized the relevance of family as ideal and appropriate for ageing and well-being towards the end of life. Co-residential living in a multi-generational household has potential health benefits in guaranteeing daily support, attention and personal optimism in old-age (Ngan, 2015 and Samanta, Chen and Vanneman, 2015). Intergenerational family care or the ‘natural support systems’ for elders is also endorsed by the state that is criticized as the abdication of the state’s responsibility to cater to its senior citizens retrenchment of the welfare state through invocation of antiquity and tradition (Victor, 2004; Lamb, 2014, Kröger, 2023). Even within the institutional setting of hospitals, there is a trend of (re)domestication, make the environment appear more ‘home-like’ and redistribute functions back to the family (Exley and Allen, 2007). Evidence suggests, a push for ageing in place and profit for the household healthcare industry, conducive for home-based services and induces commodification of care and marketization of intimacy (Ungerson, 1997; Aronson and Neysmith, 1996). The formal care sector or social care comprises of state-administered services, for-profit private enterprises or non-profit private market-based services.

Besides the moral injunctions, intergenerational solidarity and sentimental values that care represents, care is functional due to its task-oriented features of planning (scheduling tasks and preparing a roster), arranging (medical supplies, food substances, personal consumption items, caregivers) and delivering care (execution of tasks in a cohesive in a strategized manner compatible to the environment, resources and personality of the older person). This makes care compete with the demands of the labour market, out-of-home employment, causes huge opportunity costs, time-intensive, stressful and monotonous. There is a high demand for specific assistance and specialized attention for impairments, disability care, cancer care, ambulatory support and surveillance to prevent risk. Together these demands (a) time (b) commitment (c) focus (c) expertise and (e) experience.

Changes in primary kin support vis-à-vis the significant rise in ‘beanpole’³ families, stem families, transnational and distant living of adult children and labour commitment of the echo

³ **Beanpole family** refers to reduction in size of family combined with increase in longevity.

boomer⁴ generation, meeting the need-based criteria for old-age care is increasingly becoming difficult. Although, digital intimacies and polymedia environment reimagines care beyond the geographical distance paradigm (Baldassar, 2016; Hjorth and Lupton, 2010), the proximate component of body carework that cannot transcend spatio-temporal boundaries pose constraints in dis-embedding and disentangling carework from the body (Twigg, 2021). As corroborated by Cohen (2011, p. 26) “the intersection of the requirement for co-presence with the unpredictability of bodies’ social and physical demands makes spatio-temporal organisation of body labour particularly tricky.” Thus, co-presence of caregivers is instrumental for carework as body adheres to its own rhythm defined by biological unpredictability and autonomous mobility. Gender identities are constructed through caring roles and such role-playing facilitates a woman’s acceptance into the world (Graham, 1991)

In a bid to address the crisis in body carework or intimate care labour in urban India, female paid home careworkers, locally known as *ayahs* are pooled into the care network of older people. Hiring *ayahs* for care service dates back to the period of British colonial Raj during which *ayahs* acted as nursemaid to the British children, and were an integral part in making of the European colonial domesticity (Banerjee, 2022). In contemporary post-colonial India, industrialization and ensued agrarian crisis prompted rural to urban migration with female migrants turning to care services including *ayah* work (Barua, Haukanes and Waldrop, 2016). Over a period of time, the cheap and affordable labour of women who were not necessarily trained in professional nursing are hired to meet the care needs in old-age in the domestic front. *Ayahs* are often deemed as nursing aides and ‘proto-nurses’. Interestingly, the trained nursing figure within the Indian discourse embodies the interpenetration of modernization, formalization and professionalization. Despite such efforts, the stigmatization and stain on the nursing profession continue to remain dominant as social identities cross-cut occupation and occupational hierarchies (Ray, 2019). The taint on the nursing profession can be traced to the recesses of history wherein the lower-caste, Christian-convert or working-class women were pooled in via medical missionary, military or philanthropic organizations. The tasks and activities of nursing marked by dealing with bodily fluids, blood, and cleaning and changing ‘dirty’ clothing and bandages made it the reserve of the lower-caste populace (Ray, 2016, 2019 and 2020).

Formal employment rate has drastically plummeted in the Global South; while the educated female labour force is largely concentrated in the ghettoized ‘service sector’. The rising care-domestic sector is within the aegis of the informal market, practises casualization (Grover, 2022). Gender remains the dominant principle and a system of social relations in organizing home-based care (Graham). Carework is part of the gender-segregated labour market which is further characterized by informalization and casualization (Østbakken et al, 2022). Care labour is subsumed within ‘unskilled labour’ as it is an extension of women’s unpaid care labour within the family, endemic to a woman’s being and nature, and hence suffers from low-market value. This influences the market price as well wherein care labour is bargained, paid low remuneration, and borders on informalization and casualization. The informal labour market

⁴ **Echo boomer** generation refers to those born between 1977 and 1994 (Quadagno, 2014).

combined with feminization of the occupation often amplifies one another. This becomes the logical extension for wage penalty, devaluation, inequity and precarity (Basu, 2020).

Situated in the backdrop of ayah-intervened ageing and care practices, this paper is geared towards elaborating on the intimate labour for older people, what it means for the ayahs to perform such intimate tasks that border on the gross and abject, negotiating patterns and cast light on the precarities encountering careworkers entailed in elder care.

Methodology: Methods and Sampling

The present paper adopts a combination of micro-ethnography in home-setting, on-site observations, 16 family case studies and telephonic and face-to-face in-depth interviews (IDIs) with 30 ayahs situated across Kolkata, West Bengal. Both the ayahs and the families belonged to the Bengali speaking community. The ayahs were shadowed both during their tasks as well separately in their homes for seated, face-to-face interviews. The ayahs were in the age group of 30 and 55, identified themselves as ‘SC’ (Scheduled Caste) and lived as tenants in the urban slums. Ayahs were interviewed in the Bengali language and the interviews were audio-recorded through informed consent. The audio transcripts were later translated verbatim in English. This was followed by etching out quotations that had resemblance across the narratives. Condensed field notes were copiously written throughout the interviews. Later those were expanded to identify themes and developed into theoretical arguments. The sample population was selected through the peer network of the author, and snowballing through the referrals of the ayahs. Identity of the ayahs are anonymized. At the outset of the interview, they were assured that they could exit the interview process or refrain from responding

specific questions. The queries delved into a broad range of themes of intimate carework. This includes the details and roster of carework, difficulties and strategies in managing bodily fluids and discharge materials, close-contact, proximal carework and its advantages and disadvantages, and what makes them endure and persist.

Caring in old-age and intertwined intimate labour

Making and re-making of tactile carework through the ‘labouring bodies’

In discussing the peculiarities of carework, Twigg (2010) points out body carework is aimed towards restoring functioning of the body and preserving bodily integrity. While planning is an essential component, biological uncertainties, emergencies and unforeseen risks can destabilize the timetable and concede to time. Body is central to performing and delivering care. Structural relations evolving out of ‘dirty work’ are organized around the body (England and Dyck, 2011). Contemporary homecare relies on hierarchies in the allocation of care labour, the duality of affect and power asymmetry in dealing with ‘leaky’ and ‘open’ bodies as orifices become the site of care, and the gradual commodification of care (ibid). The transfer of intimate labour to the sphere of paid care dis-embeds intimacy from the family sphere and push towards the commodification and commercialization of care.

It is also the tactile element of carework that render it ambivalent. Based on regimes and institutions, through an assertion of biopower, the body undergoes disciplining, that eventuates to self-governance in the presence of ‘other’ bodies. This is articulated through the cultural caveats and its proscriptions, prescriptions and sanctions for the body that shapes attitudes towards bodies. In certain cultures, there are restrictions to ‘touching’ people of the opposite sex whereas in some cultures bodily contact is permitted under certain circumstances. Across cultures, touching or bodily contact without consent is deemed as inappropriate and construed as harassment. The body is cultural (Helman, 2007), that is made, remade and unmade through the trajectory of history and acquires meanings through a trajectory. This renders the body as ‘sacred’ and ‘private’.

Apart from this, the body whether it is through the colonial, biomedical or the capitalist lineage is viewed as ‘inferior’, ‘objectified’, requiring control and disciplining, and those visibly doing labour that demands contact with the body are stigmatized. In the medical profession hierarchy is marked by distantiation from the body (Twigg, 2000). This buttresses the division of labour between doctor and the nurses. Within nursing, it is the junior nurses or ayahs who perform the most menial, undesirable and residual tasks (Basu, 2020). This corroborates to what Twigg (2000) has stated about the hierarchical configuration within nursing and distancing from body carework with vertical upward mobility in the form of promotion. The wide definition of bodywork spans the centrality of working on the physicality and the materiality of the body along with encountering and cleaning body waste (Cohen, 2011).

Ambivalence and disgust with the bodily substances that are sticky, slimy and odorous, and compartmentalization of human anatomy into different zones of ‘desirable’ and undesirable’ play a critical factor in outsourcing carework as found from the testimonials of the families and the ayahs alike. Meena Gopal (2013) contends that it is an upper-caste privilege to distance from ‘polluting’ tasks. Transferring these tasks to lower-caste, lower class women mark the interlocking of caste, class, labour, hygiene and gender. The non-labouring upper-caste worldview of sanctity preserved through deference and distantiation from labouring activities emerges as the normative and the performative as can be seen from sharing or doling out carework lingering on the idea of ‘material’ and ‘symbolic’ pollution.

In fact, ayahs reported that they diffuse room freshener in the room of the patient to prevent odour from interfering with the daily lives of family members and stifle inconvenience. Patients who are bed-ridden and incapacitated, their excretory activities take place in the bed or adjacent to the bed. Ayahs refer to this as ‘*nongra porishkar kora*’ or ‘*moila porishkar kora*’ (cleaning dirt).

“Jaader chagiye tulte hoto, tara uhte pare na, haath te pare na, nongra porishkar kore dite hoto” (I had to clean the ‘dirt’ of patients who required hoisting due to their inability to walk and move around!) – Tapasee, 32, North 24 Parganas (Kolkata, West Bengal, India)

“Ekta boyoshko manush tar moila felte gele, ghenna toh lagbei, majhe majhe toh bomi kore diyi, bhaat-er sate” (I feel disgusted while cleaning dirt of an elderly person and at times, I vomit due to abomination) --- Banalata, 54, North 24 Parganas

Hoisting patients to clean their dirt demands vigour and physical strength, and ayahs need to demonstrate their physical strength while lifting a patient. They refer to such patients as *chagano* (lifting) patients that translates to hoisting and carrying. They found that bodies become ‘loose’, uncontrolled and gets heavy (*shorir chhere deowa*) with *boyosh* (threshold age⁵). Such ‘unbounded bodies’ due to bodily disintegration and emission of residual substances evokes repulsion (Lawton, 1998). Anything that breaches the image of a body being ‘taken care of’ calls for obviating and restoring to ‘normalcy’. Unregulated wetting, also known as “night time accidents”; the essence of dealing with bodies that are frail means that these are “in between” bodies (Mittens and Barker, 1995). As remarked by Tulle (2014) A body in decline represents breaching the cultural norms and an indication for greater grasp over it through intense control. Care is provided in tandem to preserve the bodily integrity, maintain hygiene standards of the body that portends to come under threat with an illness onset, and aestheticize ageing bodies to erase signs that reminds of illness, suffering and degeneration. Rubbing body lotion to conceal smell and creating the impression of a moisturized skin are a logical extension in this line. Disintegration or physiological incontinence in old-age becomes one of the principal factors for hiring ayahs. It serves as a route of avoidance, for family members of the older person, against confronting afflictions and the biological changes of an ageing body.

Ayahs and intimate labour in old-age care

Ayahs perform a cluster of tasks for the older patients that can be subsumed as intimate labour. These include brushing and washing the mouth, shaving beard and underarms, bathing, feeding, assistance with body waste discharge (Refer to Table 2). Close-contact with ageing bodies creates possibilities of growing familiar to the spatiality and interiority of ageing bodies. This familiarity with the corporeal disposition and anatomy of an older person knits the ayah to the patient into filiation and dependencies. Becoming acquainted with an ayah is a tacit comfort with the uniqueness of her ‘touch’ while carrying out such intimate tactile activities. However, such bodily intimacies are not without its ambivalence, predicaments, and incidences of violences for either party.

Table 1: List of Body carework		
Shaving beard	Shaving underarms	Chipping off nails
Bathing (full-body/shoulder bath)	Drying	Washing hair
Brushing teeth	Cleaning mouth	Applying toothpaste on toothbrush

⁵ The term **threshold age** refers to the onset of old-age

Measure of urine discharge	Cleaning faecal substance	Installing urinary catheter and bedpan
Applying powder, lotion or cream	Combing hair	Massage for pain relief and facilitate blood circulation

Delineating disgust and avoidance of material pollution

Mary Douglas (1966) links repulsion towards body waste with the overall discomfort with dirt. The notion of dirt has semblance with disorder or “matter out of place”. Hence the concomitant urgency to fix it and restore orderliness. Dirt represents anomaly that could potentially breach social organization. The routine standards of hygiene have semblance with purity and pollution intrinsic to Hinduism. Curtis and Biran (2001) identify five main elicitors of disgust (1) bodily excretion (2) spoilt food (3) certain living organisms (4) the ‘other’ categories of people (5) breach of social norms. Out of these bodily secretions is the primary cause of disgust- The sensory cues, the tactile feeling of sliminess and clammy, and sight of disgusting objects. Feeling of disgust stems from the distaste response. Drawing on Miller (1997) the authors argue that history of disgust is rooted in salvaging the body and soul from contacting pollution. Societies that are more rule-dense will have lower threshold of disgust. Disgust lingers on the ideas of organic. Gross pollution threatens to cause defilement (Ackroyd, 2007) through the permeation of or encounter with the “less attractive” (Twigg, 2000) and “devitalizing” (Brännström et al, 2010) aspects of the body like bodily emissions that cannot be contained and crosses boundaries. Smell has a boundary-transgressing quality as it escapes and crosses boundaries. This encroaches individual autonomy and disturbs bodily boundaries.

Aversion is “intuitive microbiology”, transmission through pathogenicity (Curtis and Biran, 2001). This explains the evocation of disgust towards ‘diseased bodies’ (Hadjittofia, Gleesona and Arber, 2020). For Julia Lawton (1998) such qualms with ‘leaky’, ‘unbounded’ and ‘open’ bodies due to bodily disintegration or physiological incontinence prompts for sequestering such bodies in old-age. Among the Bengalis, the notion of fluid and open personhood portends contamination and moral pollution as one comes in contact with the ‘impurities’ of the human body (Lamb, 2000). It refers to the intersubstantial relationships and “fluidity of enclosures” leading to transformative transactions. There could be transfer of substantial properties through mutual touching and exchange during corporeal encounters. Disgust sensitivity influences career preferences like choosing pharmacy over nursing as it involves direct care on the bodies (Consedine, Yu and Windsor, 2013). For Ousey and Roberts (2016) malodorous wounds evoke disgust and struggle for coping. There is a dilemma in being true to one’s nursing duty through ameliorating vulnerability and at the same time, the emotionally overwhelming feeling of handling exudating wounds. The authors also note that living with malodorous wounds is distressing for the patients too as they equally feel disgusted, it wrecks their self-esteem and hope, and gradually lead to isolation. Lamb (ibid, p. 37) notes that this sharing and exchange is done with the intention of establishing kin relations through birth, marriage, cohabitation and sharing food. Contamination occurs through “mutual touching” as there is a “mutual transfer

of substantial qualities”. This is rooted in managing dirt and impurities. It also explains the reservation of eating food cooked by a group or a person as potentially polluting as it is believed the one who is cooking, the qualities of that person permeate into the food. The cleanliness and hygiene norms as evident in ayahs compulsorily bathing after completion of duty marks cleaning not only the bodily pollutants but the bodily substances that transfers during carework. These transferrable properties are termed as “dravya” as articulated by Marriott (1976) and Daniel (1984). The underlying fear of substantial exchange results in moral ambiguity and predicament in doing carework.

Organizing abject labour/Kharap kaaj

*Amader bari'r lok amader haath'er ranya khabe na, jodi jante pare amader ki ki korte hoye!
(Our family members will not accept food cooked by us, on knowing the tasks we have to perform!) – Mita, 10 years of ayah care service, South 24- Parganas*

Despite its essentiality abound, ayahs are subjected to discrimination and some of them consider this as *kharap kaaj* or abject labour as it entails an everydayness of normalization and routinization of dirt, filth, phlegm, excreta and body secretion. This idea also extends to encountering end-of-life care patients and their impurities. As stated by Lee (2008), the death taboo stems from the death-denying society. In India, talking about death or being part of a labour force that encounters with death for livelihood amounts to taboo. This is reminiscent of Jonathan Parry's (1994) findings from his fieldwork in Banaras wherein families of shopkeepers selling funeral materials adhered to a low profile as they had to 'live off death'. He remarked establishment of cremation ghats outside the precincts of human settlements are in continuation to such worldview. For ayahs, the idea of 'bad death' or 'perverse death' is rooted in suffering in the social world that permeates the body, and intensifies pain, bodies that are at the brink of disintegration contravening its bounded state, and foul smell, incontinence and difficulty in eating. Albeit being at the forefront of care, these amount to the profanity and indignity of ayahs. Ray (2019, p. 90) writes "...nursing was peculiarly marked out stigmatized caste-based occupation. This stigma meant that for nursing to be recast as respectable labour, it had to be framed as *seba*, rooted in religious and spiritual ethos."

The theoretical framework show relation among disgust (*ghenna*), pathogenicity and contravention. Stemmed from the pathogenicity of the novel corona virus during the first two waves of Covid-19, and combined with atypical perceptions of care workforce in this case lower-caste women coming from the urban slums bereft of hygiene concern and physical distancing family members were reluctant in allowing 'running ayahs'⁶ to the precincts of home. The taint and stigma grew worsened for women, in this case, ayahs who are engaged in servile and somatic labour outside the kin relations. Drawn from the ethnographic findings,

⁶ In the ayah-subculture, running ayahs refer to those who commute regularly from their residence to the place of their client's residence

enlisted below are the principal causes of abjection and stigma associated with ayah care labour for older people.

- (a) Every day and routine contact with the ‘undesirable’ elements or **human dirt** including malodorous wounds, excretory materials, and bodily fluids.
- (b) A belief of **transfer of qualities/properties** or substantial exchange on touching the above-mentioned bodily impurities.
- (c) **Attending to bodies in end-of-life care.**
- (d) **Incidences of inappropriate proximity** with another body ensuing to sexual harassment, forbidden intimacies, and ambivalent care labour.

Navigating precarities and brokering care

While low-waged home care workers hired for personal care of older people resemble attendants and nursing aides in the formal, institutional settings, the former’s workplace within the informality and intimate space of ‘home’ serve as the primary difference (Aron and Neysmith). Home care aides in Stacey’s (2005) study mentioned that the primary risks of their labour were overworking, risk and, the element of emotional and physical strain. Hadjittofia, Gleesona and Arber (2020) argue that nurses provide support to patients and in doing so suppress their emotions that results in boundary blurring, depersonalisation, decreased feeling of empathy and burnout. Consistent to her arguments, ayahs experience a range of emotions due to daily exposure to somatic material substances, violent outburst from their patients and insensitive attitude of co-residential family caregivers. Paid home carework closely mirrors paid domestic work in India that is perceived as a ‘contact space’ involving interaction between unequal parties and asymmetrical relationship through dynamic negotiations known as boundary work (Barua, Haukanes and Waldrop, 2016). Malati, an ayah, offers insight on what it feels like to attend to a patient with faecal incontinence. As narrated by her, the older lady under her care could earlier self-manage her excretory activities. Later, she lost control of her bodily functions and would often get submerged in excreta. This caused difficulty for Malati but she was quick to point out that for *dida* (a kinship terminology for grandmother in Bengali language system), the situation was quite helpless. Feminisation aside, devaluation and penalty of carework has roots in the caste-class lineages. Hence, the dichotomies between prestigious and dirty are further sharpened (Ray, 2020).

Locating repulsion in material pollution

The aversion to body wastes lies in its separation from the body, yet it is perceived as being part of the body and the environment that disconcerts the notion of a “free-standing entity”, defying the order (Zerubavel, 1991). This brings to the paradox of body carework--- its indispensability in keeping older adults hygienic, well-groomed and confident whereas in simultaneity, there is socially and morally tainted character (Mills and Schejbal, 2007) owing to the suppression and acceptance of aversion or abject labour for livelihood by the marginalized actors.

Sabitri who has been 8 years in care service and was approached through a domestic helper stated that in her initial phase to evade the overpowering effect of odour, she would cover her nose with a handkerchief. Through her carework period, she has grown accustomed to bad

smell. She expressed her triumph in taming disgust sensitivity in her early-stage of service to now in control of her repulsion. This visceral feeling of *ghenna* or disgust, a leitmotif of intimate carework, is an all-consuming, overpowering and all-encompassing emotion. Coping and adapting comes at the cost of desensitization. The obverse suggests, those who cannot quell their aversion flounder to perform carework. Due to these, some ayahs preferred childcare instead of elder care. Despite efforts to overcome repulsion, the image of body waste and the physical experience of cleaning it is overwhelming, unsettling and disturbing.

The explicit disadvantages of intimate labour are negotiated with assessing the favourable outcome and advantages of ayah care service. Jaba, an ayah shared vivid detail of her distressing experience of cleaning the excretory region of an older woman who is incapacitated, had to be hoisted⁷ for daily activities. Internalisation and normalization of dirt as an innate component of servile work especially healing labour is common among ayahs, another indication of the gender-caste lineage wherein the marginalized actors are responsible for cleanliness and hygiene preservation. Ayahs straddle with the conflict of revelation regarding the exact details of their tasks. Jaba who had served as an ayah in the institutional setting of hospitals before moving to home care mentioned of censoring and eliding work-related conversations on filth and dirt with her family members. This was stemmed by a fear that on awareness, food cooked by her will not be accepted by them. Pointed out by Lamb (2000), the notion intersubstantial exchange is hinged in the belief that the one who touches a polluting substance imbibes that quality. This also explains the activity of bathing and cleaning by the ayahs after conclusion of their daily tasks and before leaving for their homes. For them, this is a way of restoring ‘normalcy’ due to the possibility of contamination and lingering dirt while *patient-er duty* or *ayah-r duty* (in this context synonymous to attending older patients).

Censoring information to family members further extends to incidences of sexual harassment. Jaba recounted of patients who would suddenly embrace her, may coax for physical intimacy while cleaning their reproductive organs or may request for masturbation. She felt such inappropriate and taboo behaviour results from absence of intimacy in old-age, effect of medicine, and loss of control on the self and retaliation through assertion of residual masculinity against frailty, degeneration and desexualisation of ageing. She further stated as bodies grow cold (*thhanda*), pining for human warmth becomes common that appears as ‘transgression of moral normative relation or boundaries’. Hence, in her opinion, not every act on these lines to be conflated with physical intimacy and need to be distinguished as a yearning for human touch, assurance and solidarity at the brink of loneliness and degeneration.

Another expression of such assertion of selfhood can be fathomed from Bala, a full-time, live-in ayahs who narrated her harrowing experience with an elder man who showed resistance in using bathroom and was insistent on discharging excretory fluids in the bed. He felt entitled that ayahs were obliged and bound to concede to his instructions as the latter were being remunerated. He fumed with anger and felt humiliated when Bala covered her nose while cleaning faecal matter. Bala in turn, did not budge from her position and made it clear to him that it is her prerogative how she manages against stench smell. She was abhorred on recounting

⁷ Such patients are called ‘chagano’, a term used for double-handed care and for lifting, within the sub-culture of Bengali speaking ayahs as discussed in Panchadhyayi, 2024 (forthcoming)

the sensorial experience especially during meals. While dignity maintenance is a critical component of carework that is often accomplished through Curtains or door serve boundary maintenance mechanisms to separate the ‘private’ and mark privacy from the outside world (Bailey, Murphy and Porock, 2011). However, ayahs have no ways to avoid confronting the nakedness of human bodies, despite

Komola, a live-in ayah who had a role-transition from a paid domestic help in a vignette, recounted an instance wherein the patient diagnosed with mid-stage dementia and dependent on urinary catheter, soiled himself and left a trail of foul-smelling faecal matter. Referring to the patient as *baba* (a kin term for the pater in Bengali) and a metaphorical parent-child like dyad facilitate in brokering care and in the face of aversion. She went onto state that she was advised to stay away from contacting faecal matter of an ill person as it contains germs. However, she felt that using gloves for hygiene is not required as he is a father-figure. This surmises that glove appeared as a symbol of barrier between here (the carer) and (the ‘cared for’). Through her statement, she tried to establish kin-like intimacy as central to navigating the entanglements and difficulties of intimate care. Komola’s account leads to a profound pathway in eldercare – fostering and building filiation, prior familiarity and eventual familiarity, and the parent-child mimesis that informs and enables coping with the predicaments of intimate body care.

In complementary to this, embracing a parental attitude invoking the image of ‘second childhood’ of older people facilitate in nullifying the awkwardness or embarrassment of nakedness. The imaging of ageing with second childhood is not understood in parallel in terms of similarities rather old age is synonymized with childhood (Hockey and James, 1995). This buttresses the role of ‘metaphoric parent’ assumed by the ayahs or taken upon by the ayahs and turning older people to ‘metaphoric children’. In the verbatim of Jaba, “*ekdum bacchader moto hoye jaye, tokhhon onek onek bhalobashte hoye (an older person completely becomes like a child and then pampering and tendering is necessary).*” While imaging older people as children reinforces them as ‘dependent’ and denies their personhood as argued by the authors. This imaging in turn, serves interlocked purposes that of excluding elders from the labour force participation and confining their caregiving needs within the sphere of the private, the family. However, as ayahs deploy the metaphor of ‘child’ it is a coping mechanism and a strategy of negotiation to deal with the difficulties, the grossness and the recalcitrant elements of carework. Imaging an older patient as a kin member stem from the duty-bound and intergenerational reciprocity for their parents and elders in the family, and the consequent abandonment and denial of care. These underwrite the universal foundation of care and its essential force especially to support the frail, the infirm, the recuperating and the lonely vulnerable older citizenry.

Continuum of home-care phenomenon

The ayahs in this study, narrated their personal reasons or vectors that offsets the negative boundaries of carework especially in comparison to paid domestic work and paid domestic culinary labour. Firstly, as opposed to range of work available in the informal labour sector, ayah care is relatively better waged compared to paid domestic service (*tola kaaj*) or paid cooking (*ranyar kaaj*). Women become part of precarious employment patterns to complement

and many a times solely support the familial earnings with the dwindling opportunities of men's employment (Palriwala, 2019). Secondly, ayahs have reported that attending a bed-ridden patient, also referred as a *showa* patient in the ayah subculture an ayah may fetch her higher wage than other patients. Deepa, with 20 years of experience was of the view installing enema and urinary catheter are skills that enables her to quote additional charges.

Thirdly, the element of well-being and ushering change due to the 'transformational labour' can render prestige and satisfaction. Relating to their labour as *seva* that is transcendental and transformational, many ayahs derived pride and dignity vis-à-vis upward mobility, and contributing to healing (*sustho kora, jotno kora, shariye tola*). Fourthly, unlike paid domestic work and paid cooking that requires managing multiple households as a livelihood strategy, tethering to one household ayah care service was viewed as an advantage as it reduced the hassle of '*dhokol*' (exhaustion) due to commuting. Together these served as a possibility for a better life, hope for vertical mobility through a shift in consumption practices and escape from the cycle of intergenerational poverty. Through their assessment of the advantages versus the disadvantages in carework, ayahs derive esteem and rank their tasks in high regards within the graded system of carework. This has semblance with Clare Stacey's (2005) study on homecare aides who derived pride and relative autonomy while doing 'dirty work'. . . Another less explored and underdiscussed aspect is the filial, kin-like and reciprocal underpinning of care becomes a motivating factor for endurance and long-term support. Cordial relations with families and integration within the household through exercising autonomy, managing resources and material endowments secured through these intimate transactions, add to the complexities of receiving, performing and persisting care labour. Body carework is dependent on the interweaving of relations between care workers, family caregivers and care recipients for responding to the materiality of the body and management of the self of the care recipient (Cohen, 2011).

Blurring boundaries and ambivalence: Resentment, resistance and agency

Bakul, an ayah while sharing her experience of attending to persons with cancer, maintained caution and remained circumspective while especially with bandaging the affected areas. For a patient with breast cancer, she had to ensure operated breast area and ensure water does not reach. The person with cancer in the anal area had to endure most excruciating pain as blood would ooze out every time he went to the bathroom and splashed across. She compared this to a woman's struggle of blood flow during her menstrual cycle. Some ayahs felt disgusted with such visuals, and this continued and affected them while consuming meal. For some ayahs the desensitization reaches to such a degree that no amount of waste matter could trigger their aversion. The 'problem of the body', the messy details and the profane aspects are sanitized, scientized and hidden in the nursing knowledge through neologisms and euphemisms (Lawler, 1991 and Williams, 2003). A major resentment that surfaced in the study was many ayahs reporting of not being distributed gloves and relying on makeshift arrangement of cloths trip, newspaper, tissue or cotton to clean faecal matter. Gloves serve as a tool of distantiating from the corporeality of intimate labour apart from professionalism (Twigg, 2000). There is hardly any barrier or symbolic protection to offset the polluting nature through more robust

availability of hygiene supplies. To imagine the ayahs managing without gloves while performing intimate care forays debate on ethics of care labour, responsibilities of family caregivers in making the home environment conducive and the synonymizing dirt with certain bodies, group and work. Jaba's humiliation as her elderly client to ayah care service as *chhoto kaaj* (*insignificant labour*) is consistent with the inferior status allocated to ayah carework. A classic representation of menial labour as further degrading and defiling with women in the bottom of the caste-order taking up such tasks (John, 2013). Marginalization and devaluation of carework is an outcome of treating it within the sphere of obligation and nurturance instead of the "realm of exchange". Along with this, the entry, presence and visibility of lower-caste women in out-of-home labour renders the occupation and women performing it as 'inferior' (Gopal, 2013). England (2005) argues that the 'public goods' framework and the concept of 'prisoner of love' underpin the inherent altruism of care, implicating low-wage and feminization of allied occupation. Devaluation, underpayment, stigmatization and peripheralization of carework is connected to the canon that care is innate to a woman's temperament, it is in her nature and hence, there are no real skills involved. It is subsumed within the broader category of nurturant work that serves negative stereotyping of carework. This also explains the pay penalty of carework (ibid). Global cities become sites of women in low-paid service sectors that results in a class of workers who are dispersed and invisible (Sassen, 2002). She went onto argue that the developing economies in the Global South establish survival circuits around women. Drawing on Sassen's (2002) argument of feminization of survival and new circuits in the global cities, it can be stated women are already in disadvantaged positions with multiple barriers to living with dignity and experiencing a safe working condition. Palriwala (2019) points out that care economy evolved out of the emerging care deficit through commodification of the private nature of care in the free labour market. Women with a historical trajectory of structural hierarchies were employed into this unorganized care labour market due to the logic of intertwining of care as feminine and women as caring. This ushered in feminization of care labour and global chain of inequality. The collusion between neo-liberal regime, gendered structure and caste politics widens the cleavages and faultlines, and shift away from active welfarism. Much like the variables of gender and ethnic identities, gender and caste location interpenetrate in the devaluation of carework, allocation of carework, overrepresentation, polarization and segregation within it and influences hierarchical ordering.

Careworkers reclaim moral authority, value and dignity through their labour as the otherwise repulsive aspect inherent in carework used for emphasizing difference gains visibility (Bolton, 2005 and Stacey, 2005). Synonymizing carework with dignity facilitates in navigating the profane and less desirable elements of the body. Wilkinson and Wilkinson (2020) implore for referring to care work as 'dignity work' rather than dirty work to salvage it from the sphere of stigma. They state that the dirty aspect of carework reinstates the self-esteem of patients and restore their dignity. The ayahs despite their confrontation with human dirt were conscious about their position and at times indispensability in filling up the vacuum of care, and being a bridge between the patient and the family caregiver. This consciousness becomes a tool in subversion of the dominant cultural ideology of old-age carework as 'dirty work', and reclaiming self-esteem and dignity. This could be interpreted as the 'hidden transcripts'

discussed by Barua, Haukanes and Waldrop in their study of domestic workers in Mumbai, India. By hidden transcripts, it refers to the covert and non-confrontational ways of exerting resilience and showing agency. The canon of social pollution, cascades into the attitude and treatment towards the ayahs right from not offering food cooked in the employer's home to refusal of drinking water to offering rugged or tattered cloth for sleeping to expecting them to have food near the bathroom or in the kitchen.

Doing carework is enmeshed in the oscillating power relations- while patients can get away with their confrontational behaviour or inimical attitude towards the ayah, 'an outsider' working in the private territory of someone else's home; on the other the dependency of patients on the ayahs and routinization of bodily exposure for care predicates the essence of body care labour. Through the proximate nature of carework, the ayahs can become a close aide, a privy to the older person's life. Komola informed that the ayah who preceded her, grew close to the older man and they developed a bond that contravened the moral boundaries. The porous boundaries of intimate care work that seems to surface at the interface of loneliness, social isolation, physical decline and finding 'home' and 'belongingness' indicates its transcendental quality. Censorship of such details and discussing in low volume are connected to the proscribed and the unacceptable. In its limits and liminalities, foregoing and enduring, and emotional immersion and detached concern, ayah care is both unique and universal. It is unique as the practices; the strategies and motivations emerge from the cultural landscape of care. On the other hand, its universality lies in the survival instinct of the historically marginalised group and the ethical responsibility of 'caring about' and 'caring for'. Intimate carework provide continuity, assurance and interweaves the community to the older person. The precarity of intimate work lies in threat of somatic integrity of careworkers, questions on safety and reporting violations, and burnout and care fatigue due to long-term caregiving.

Conclusion

Ayahs are part of the nurturant reproductive⁸ care workforce marked by face-to-face interactions, relational skills and services that take place in the backstage context. Flexibility, easy hire-and-fire, opportunity costs of the informal labour market, relative higher wage and dignity are the leitmotifs ayah care service. While demographic shift and its consequences for the older citizenry have gradually started occupying both academic and public sphere, the precarity shadowing the careworkers and their rights to be treated with dignity is neglected. The moral compass, care as a universal social good and a binding force in braiding together institutions trump over the constituents of fatigue, discomfort, anguish, devaluation and humiliation faced by the careworkers. The affective-intimacy of carework lies in overcoming boundaries of purity and pollution, hygiene and dirt, and self and other that is a striking feature of carework that separates it from overlapping occupation of paid domestic work. The moral dilemma of intimate carework emerged saliently among the careworkers as they straddle

⁸ **Reproductive carework** involves nonrelational activities, takes place in the backstage like cooking and cleaning, and demands physical rigour.

between healing and promoting the well-being of their older clients while grappling with the material pollution that is a defining feature of such nursing-nurturing labour.

Boundaries and bindings are central to ayah care labour in retaining the personhood of ageing selves, frailty, declining condition, and grappling at the cusp of living and dying. Fostering continuities through kinning marks the transaction beyond being informed by money. It is the relational aspect of care labour that enables ayahs to reclaim their subjectivities, derive prestige while restoring dignity for selves in incontinence and providing succour through vulnerable episodes make many of them see their labour in a new light – healing and transformational labour. Albeit its imbrications/conflations with the gamut of domestic services, these intimate transactions order and earmark elder care as a separate category on the grounds of (a) exigency-emergency component (b) recuperation, well-being and reintegration channelled by emotional-corporeal labour and (c) close-contact with the body for assistive living and ADL (assisted daily living).

This directs to a concatenation of blindspots for thinking through and taking up future research (1) Firstly, the multi-sensory component of intimate labour that permeates through porous boundaries and thrives in the memory hardly receives much attention. (2) To find purpose in ‘dirty’ and ‘taboo’ work is the indomitable human spirit of making life liveable. The emotional preparedness in intimate care labour is the second blindspot. Since it is difficult to quantify emotions, the traumatizing effect of disgust on ayahs and their coping skills are neither rewarded nor remunerated. (3) The third blindspot is that ayahs engaged in intimate work and in the course may develop intimacy lingering on the domain of taboo. (4) The fourth blindspot is the tensions and confrontations that may emerge between the family caregiver and the ayah on grounds of retaining ‘dirty work’ that part from being tied to hierarchy fosters closeness as vulnerability can make one feel close to the one in actual co-presence and doing intimate tasks. (5) The fifth blindspot is that ayahs are involved in ‘caring’ and ‘curing’, prompting the question whether occupations related to ‘cure’ is more valued, compensated and revered as compared to occupations of ‘caring’. Tending and attending to ageing bodies is to do with grooming.

Ayahs are the front-line essential service providers in both home and the institutional settings. Reconciliation between the moral-ethical goal of ageing with dignity and consolidation of the rights of the careworkers/*ayahs* are necessary. Through their involvement in well-being and alleviation of sufferings, ayahs participate in a panoply of tasks that facilitate home-care for the grey population in urban India. While risks loom large, ayahs take up the herculean task of risk mitigation and provides a sense of continuity of selfhood. Although, they have emerged as a key addition in the care network in the urban sphere, invisibilization of their labour through imbricating them with paid domestic work and paid cooking is rather blinkered as it denies their distinctiveness in specializing in care and health. Their marginalization in the social matrix is compounded vis-à-vis denial of their knowledge, skills and practices of care due to the medical hierarchy of knowledge. Unlike nurses who are widely recognized as a paramedical force in the professional healthcare system (Helman, 2007), the ethnomedical knowledge of the ayahs are overshadowed by their servile and marginal history.

Long-term care (LTC) sector in the west is dependent on the paraprofessional workers who constitute the main care providers for frail elders at home (Aronson and Neysmith, 1996), while for Indian cities as established through archival findings *ayahs* have always been a silenced and invisibilized figure only with the neo-liberal and globalized their contribution in contemporality is galvanizing research interests. With nursing care being expensive, to cut-cost urban families in India are opting for *ayahs* to dispose of labour that family caregivers cannot perform. While acknowledging the penalty of feminization of labour, exploitation faced by careworkers as it is part of the unorganized sector and negotiating the disgust and stigma, care is essential. Therefore, developing a robust homecare model compatible to the target population of older people.

Graham points out the care policy perspectives that latches onto the ‘location’ and ‘social relations’ dimensions of care, tend to present care within home as informal spearheaded by unpaid family carers. This model of intergenerational-obligatory care becomes the normative and the performative code for home careworkers who are hired for elder care. Burning bridges and building policies in tandem with dignity and rights of older people complementing the interests of the *ayahs* are part of the rights-based narrative.

Some of the proposed recommendations is that homecare model should be developed keeping in mind the heterogeneity of the target urban population (the oldest old, onset age, gender, retired, living arrangement, number of caregivers both proximate and co-residential, residential type including gated estate, illness trajectory, assistive technology, economic resources including health insurance, pension, savings and financial assistance from family. Home care model should be cognizant of the interests of both the outsourced help (*ayahs*) and the recipients of care. Availability of hygiene supplies including masks, gloves, headgears, apron, protective glasses, slippers in the household, dustpan and soaps depending on the kind of older person, access to clean and portable water, monitoring the *ayah*-family relationships through a feedback loop, harnessing the knowledge of the *ayahs* and, support mechanisms for both the actors to address grievances are fundamental to chartering care relationships and dignity. Suggestions from family caregivers and older clients could also bridge gap and alleviate tensions within the care matrix.

With the lack of regulation of the informal labour market, arbitrary wage structure, unsafe work environment, private home as the as the workplace, lack of transparency and accountability about the details of tasks, oral agreements that are violable, and unavailability of hygiene supplies poses fork in the road for the *ayahs*. Resilience and adaptation of the *ayahs* must not conflate or romanticize their struggles. Rather this should be treated as a wake-up call to improve homecare and strive towards cohesive pathways of care. Policy innovation oriented towards safe and dignified care conditions for the care recipients and working conditions of the paid caregivers alike is exigent.

Figure 1. Homecare model in improving care conditions

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